

IDENTIFICATION OF DISTRIBUTED MALWARE

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Abstract: Mobile phones have transitioned from basic communication tools to sophisticated handheld computers, equipped with numerous applications that enhance the significance of personal data. This transformation renders these devices attractive targets for cybercriminals, especially Android, which is the most widely used and open-source operating system, drawing the attention of various malware creators.

Malware has evolved from simple infections to advanced threats, such as distributed denial-of-service (DDoS) attacks using botnets. A notable emerging trend is the rise of a new type of distributed malware on Android, where applications that appear innocuous on their own can collaborate to carry out harmful actions. This paper introduces the concept of this distributed malware, explores its capacity to bypass existing security measures, and presents detection techniques utilizing graph matching algorithms.

Keywords: malware, botnet, DDOS, Android malware, distributed malware, syntactic feasibility.

I. INTRODUCTION

Mobile devices have undergone significant changes since their launch in the early 1970s, evolving from bulky machines to the sleek, programmable smartphones we know today. Currently, around 75% of smartphone users utilize devices that run on the Android operating system, making it a prime target for malware creators. With these advancements in technology, vulnerabilities in their systems have also become more prevalent. For decades, malware has been a serious threat to computing devices, and it was only a matter of time before attackers shifted their focus to popular mobile platforms like Symbian [1].

A variety of malware types have been created to circumvent device security measures, with cybercriminals continually finding new ways to exploit these weaknesses, posing serious risks to users. Malware is designed to damage user data while remaining hidden, taking advantage of flaws in operating systems. Starting in 2004, concerns about the potential for malware to target mobile devices were voiced in various articles. [6] Since then, the incidence of malware aimed at smartphones has surged.

Figure 1. Emerging Malware Variants

Figure 1 illustrates the increasing prevalence of new malware samples across Android platforms. In recent years, there has been a notable rise in new malware samples specifically targeting Android platforms. From 2020 to 2023, the frequency of these malware attacks has increased significantly, indicating a persistent threat that necessitates updates to current security protocols to reduce potential damage. As the popularity of these platforms grows, they inevitably become attractive targets for malware developers. [5]

The role of app marketplaces complicates security efforts, making it difficult to conduct thorough scans of every application. This oversight can lead to widespread vulnerabilities affecting numerous devices in a very short time. A prime example is the malware known as DroidDream, which affected more than 530,000 devices within just 20 to 70 hours before Google managed to remove all related malicious applications from the Play Store. In light of these ongoing threats, there is an increasing call for app store curators to implement more stringent reviews of applications before granting permission for publication. While app stores do filter applications based on various

security criteria, many users often download apps from less secure sources, overlooking potential security risks.[2] This behavior contributes to the rise of malicious applications disguised as viruses, adware, worms, and trojans, which are capable of stealing personal data, executing harmful code, and degrading device performance. To combat these threats, Google has developed a security system known as Bouncer, which employs dynamic analysis to detect and filter out malicious applications from its Play Store. Bouncer evaluates uploaded apps and associated developer accounts through its cloud infrastructure and reputation engine. Although Google claims that Bouncer has led to a 55% decrease in the number of malicious apps on its platform, researchers, including Miller and Oberheide, have pointed out weaknesses in Bouncer's detection process [7]. A key concern is that Bouncer's dynamic analysis typically lasts only 2 to 4 minutes, which may not be enough time to catch all malicious behaviors, especially if an app only misbehaves outside the analysis window. As a result, while Bouncer successfully identifies some harmful applications during runtime, it may overlook those that do not exhibit malicious activity in such a limited timeframe.

The flexible nature of the Android platform allows users to access applications from various locations, including external storage devices and internet sites. While this accessibility is beneficial, it also raises the concern of potentially installing harmful software on devices unintentionally. To tackle such threats, a range of strategies for identifying malware has been created, from basic methods relying on static signatures to more complex techniques that incorporate machine learning. Each strategy has its pros and cons. Nonetheless, when considering both effectiveness and user-friendliness, static analysis tends to be recognized as the most dependable method, particularly when paired with current machine learning (ML) [8], [9], [10] and deep learning [13] [14], [15],[16] technologies. A crucial aspect of developing a successful ML-based detection system is the careful choice of the feature set utilized by the algorithms. If features demand excessive processing resources for extraction, they can slow down overall system performance, whereas irrelevant or inadequate features can lead to poor

detection outcomes. Additionally, this paper introduces a new type of distributed malware, enriching the ongoing discussion regarding malware detection approaches.

II. SUGGESTED METHOD

Distributed malware is a collection of applications that individually appear harmless, but when they operate simultaneously, they can trigger malicious behavior. These applications function without revealing any signs of wrongdoing; their actions mimic those of benign software. As a result, their covert activities occur quietly in the background, making it challenging to identify any threats they might pose.

Figure 2: Four harmless applications

To illustrate this concept, imagine four harmless applications, as depicted in Figure 2. Application 1 is already active, prompting application 2 to begin its execution. Following this, application 2 triggers application 3, which in turn launches application 4. This sequence creates a pattern, as illustrated in Figure 3. Although this collection comprises benign applications, it has the potential to function as malware. Any application can trigger the execution of one or more other applications, resulting in various initiators for a single application, which complicates detection efforts even further.

Figure 3: Suspected Malicious Sequence

Applications utilize intents and services for interaction. Intents serve as signals to the Android system, notifying it of specific events and detailing the actions to be executed along with relevant data. [4] For instance, an intent to open an Excel file will trigger the app to load that file. In contrast, services are components that carry out prolonged tasks in the background without displaying a user interface. [3] They can interact with other components and enable inter-process communication (IPC). For example, a service might be responsible for playing music, managing file processes, or overseeing network transactions[12].

To determine whether the pattern on the device is malicious or benign, a database containing known malicious patterns will be utilized. The VF2 algorithm will perform the comparison between the two graphs $G_1=(N_1,E_1)$ and $G_2=(N_2,E_2)$. This matching process relies on a mapping M , which consists of pairs (n,m) , where $n \in G_1$ and $m \in G_2$. Each pair indicates the correspondence between a node n in G_1 and a node m in G_2 .

METHOD MATCH(S)

PROCEDURE Match

INPUT: an intermediate state s ;

the initial state s_0 has $M(s_0) = \emptyset$

OUTPUT: the mappings between the two graphs

IF $M(s)$ covers all the nodes of G_2 THEN

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OUTPUT M(s0)
RETURN
END IF
P(s) ← ComputeCandidatePairs(s)
FOREACH p IN P(s)
IF FeasibilityRules(s, p) THEN
PrecomputeDataStructures(s, p)
s' ← AddPairToState(s, p)
Match(s')
RestoreDataStructures(s, p)
END IF
END FOREACH
END PROCEDURE Match

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Figure 4. VF2 Graph Matching Algorithm [11]

State Space Representation (SSR) is utilized to compute the mapping function in this process. In the matching procedure, each state s corresponds to a portion of the mapping solution $M(s)$, which is a subset of the complete mapping M . Specifically, $G_1(s)$ and $G_2(s)$ are subgraphs of G_1 and G_2 that are defined by $M(s)$. These subgraphs are obtained by selecting nodes from G_1 and G_2 that are part of $M(s)$, including the connecting edges between them.

The algorithm uses a set of feasibility rules to verify the conditions necessary for creating consistent states. A feasibility function $F(s,n,m)$ is employed, which returns true if the addition of the pair (n,m) to the state s satisfies all the feasibility rules. The function is defined as:

$$F(s,n,m) = F_{\text{syn}}(s,n,m) \wedge F_{\text{sem}}(s,n,m)$$

where F_{syn} (syntactic feasibility) ensures structural compatibility, and F_{sem} (semantic feasibility) ensures compatibility in terms of node attributes. Initially, the mapping function is empty, i.e., $M(s_0)=\emptyset$. At each intermediate state, the algorithm computes the set $P(s)$, which contains candidate node pairs that can be added to the current state. The feasibility rules are applied to each pair in $P(s)$. If the feasibility check passes, i.e., if $F(s,n,m)$ is true, the successor state $s'=s\cup(n,m)$ is computed, and the matching process continues recursively from s' . All possible pairs in $P(s)$ are evaluated and added to the current state, with priority given to nodes directly connected to $G_1(s)$ and $G_2(s)$. The sets $T_{1\text{out}}(s)$ and $T_{2\text{out}}(s)$ represent the target branches of $G_1(s)$ and $G_2(s)$ and are not yet part of the partial mapping. Similarly, $T_{1\text{in}}(s)$ and $T_{2\text{in}}(s)$ represent the starting branches of $G_1(s)$ and $G_2(s)$ that are also not yet included in the partial mapping. The set $P(s)$ consists of node pairs (n,m) , where m belongs to $T_{2\text{out}}(s)$ and n belongs to $T_{1\text{out}}(s)$. If either of these sets is empty, the algorithm considers node pairs from $T_{1\text{in}}(s)$ and $T_{2\text{in}}(s)$ instead.

III. CONCLUSION

With the growing adoption of smartphones, there arises a significant responsibility to address the existing vulnerabilities within the Android ecosystem. One such critical vulnerability is distributed malware, which poses a greater threat due to its distributed nature and potential to cause more damage than the traditional malware we have been combating. This paper has discussed the concept of distributed malware, its formation, and the amplified risks it presents. Additionally, we have explored how graph matching algorithms can be leveraged to detect and mitigate the effects of such distributed threats.

REFERENCES

- [1] Kim, K. H., & Choi, M. J., "Android malware detection using multivariate time-series technique" Asia-Pacific Network Operations and Management Symposium

(APNOMS), 27–34.2016.

[2] Jaiswal, M., Malik, Y., & Jaafar, F. Android gaming malware detection using system call analysis. International Symposium on Digital Forensic and Security (ISDFS), 172–177, 2018.

[3] T, Alper, D. I., & Aydin, C. APK Auditor: A permission-based Android malware detection system. Digital Investigation, 13, 1–14.2020.

[4] Talha, K. A., Alper, D. I., & Aydin, C., “APK Auditor: A permission-based Android malware detection system” Digital Investigation, 13, 1-14, 2020.

[5] T. Blasing, L. Batyuk, A. D. Schmidt, S. A. Camtepe, and S. Albayrak, “An android application sandbox system for suspicious software detection”, Malicious and Unwanted Software (MALWARE) International Conference, 2010.

[6] D. Dagon, T. Martin, and T. Starner, “Mobile phones as computing devices: The viruses are coming!”, IEEE Pervasive Computing, vol. 3, no. 4, pp. 11-15, 2004.

[7] J. Oberheide and C. Miller, “Dissecting the Android Bouncer” SummerCon, 2019.

[8] L. Apvrille and A. Apvrille, “Identifying unknown android malware with feature extractions and classification techniques”, in Trustcom/BigDataSE/ISPA IEEE, vol. 1., 2015, pp. 182-189.

[9] L. Batyuk, M. Herpich, S. A. Camtepe, K. Raddatz, A.-D. Schmidt, and S. Albayrak, “Using static analysis for automatic assessment and mitigation of unwanted and malicious activities within android applications”, in MALWARE’11 IEEE, 2011.

[10] J. Saxe and K. Berlin, “Deep neural network based malware detection using two dimensional binary program features”, 10th International Conference on Malicious and unwanted Software(MALWARE), 2015.

[11] Cordella, L. P., Foggia, P., Sansone, C., & Vento, M. (2001). A (sub)graph isomorphism algorithm for matching large graphs. IEEE Transactions on Pattern Analysis and Machine Intelligence, 26(10), 1367–1372.

[12] S. Khemani, D. Jain, G. Prasad, “Android Malware Detection Techniques”, 5 th

International Conference on ERCICA, 2018.

[13] Umirzakova, S.; Mardieva, S.; Muksimova, S.; Ahmad, S.; Whangbo, T. Enhancing the Super-Resolution of Medical Images: Introducing the Deep Residual Feature Distillation Channel Attention Network for Optimized Performance and Efficiency. *Bioengineering* **2023**, *10*, 1332.

[14] Muksimova, S.; Umirzakova, S.; Kang, S.; Cho, Y. I. CerviLearnNet: Advancing cervical cancer diagnosis with reinforcement learning-enhanced convolutional networks. *Heliyon* **2024**, *10* (9), e29913 DOI: 10.1016/j.heliyon.2024.e29913.

[15] Umirzakova, S. Ahmad, S. Mardieva, S. Muksimova, T.K. Whangbo. Deep learning-driven diagnosis: a multi-task approach for segmenting stroke and Bell's palsy. *Pattern Recogn.*, 144 (2023).

[16] Muksimova, S.; Umirzakova, S.; Mardieva, S.; Cho, Y.-I. Enhancing Medical Image Denoising with Innovative Teacher–Student Model-Based Approaches for Precision Diagnostics. *Sensors* **2023**, *23*, 9502. <https://doi.org/10.3390/s23239502>.